

Research Paper

Physical pretreatment of three biowastes to improve black soldier fly larvae bioconversion efficiency

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ABSTRACT

Black soldier fly larvae (BSFL, *Hermetia illucens* (L.)) are recognized for efficient biowaste reduction while yielding valuable proteins and fats for animals. However, lignocellulosic fibers in biowastes are difficult to digest by biowaste and larval digestive tract microorganisms as well as the larvae themselves. This study investigated two biowaste physical pretreatments (thermal, mechanical) for improving BSFL processing of fibrous biowastes. Cow manure, spent grain, and grass clippings were thermally pretreated at 90 °C for three durations (0.5, 1 and 4 h). Contrary to expectations, thermal pretreatment resulted in either no improvement or decreased larval performance on all substrates, regardless of treatment duration. In contrast, mechanical pretreatment of spent grain and grass clippings, involving milling with three screen sizes (0.5, 1 and 2 mm) showed promising results. Specifically, bioconversion rates on 0.5 mm-milled spent grain and grass clippings increased by 0–53 % and 25–44 % dry mass, respectively compared to untreated. Additionally, larval protein conversion increased by 41 % and 23 % on spent grain and grass clippings, respectively. However, mechanical pretreatment did not affect fiber degradation by larval conversion, as hemicellulose decreased by 25 % and 75 % for spent grain and grass clippings, respectively, regardless of particle size. Particle size reduction influenced substrate microbial respiration (CO₂ mg/min), with 0.5-mm milled grass clippings exhibiting higher respiration compared to untreated, although this effect was not observed for spent grain. This study highlights mechanical pretreatment's potential in enhancing BSFL bioconversion of fibrous biowastes and the importance of understanding substrate physical properties influencing substrate microorganisms and BSFL.

1. Introduction

Rapid urbanization due to population growth, exceeding 9 billion people by 2050, intensifies waste management challenges as expanding cities and thriving economies contribute to increased waste generation. Currently, the world generates 2 billion tons of waste annually, of which 33 % is inadequately managed (Kaza et al., 2018). Among this waste, food and green biowaste constitutes the largest fraction, accounting for 44 % of the total waste (Kaza et al., 2018). Poor waste management poses risks to public health, such as higher incidences of diarrhea and acute respiratory infections for those near open dump sites (UN-Habitat, 2010). Innovative approaches that can reuse biowaste and generate

revenue, thereby offsetting the costs to manage the waste are needed. Among these approaches, black soldier fly larvae (*Hermetia illucens*, L., BSFL) have emerged as a promising biowaste treatment technology, efficiently recycling nutrients from various biowastes into insect biomass rich in protein (32–58 % dry mass, DM) and fat (15–39 % DM) suitable for animal feed and aquaculture applications (Gold et al., 2018). Furthermore, the residual by-product left by BSFL is rich in nutrients, bioactive compounds, and beneficial microorganisms with value as soil conditioners and/or organic fertilizer (Fuhrmann et al., 2022; Poveda, 2021). By incorporating feeds derived from BSFL, there is potential to reduce reliance on environmentally concerning resources such as fish and soybean meal (Vongvichith et al., 2020).

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Despite their ability to grow on a diverse range of biowastes, a major obstacle for this emerging biowaste technology is their unreliable and inefficient growth on fibrous biowastes containing lignocellulosic fibers (i.e., lignin, cellulose, hemicellulose) (Peguero et al., 2022). Consequently, this limitation can result in lower bioconversion rates (2–6 % DM) compared to bioconversion rates on highly nutritious feeds (>15 % DM), resulting in a reduced product yield per unit of waste, thus impacting the amount of product and revenue that can be generated. Furthermore, performance variability hampers product consistency and reliability, posing a challenge when attempting to create a profitable business from the upcycling of biowaste.

Lignocellulosic fibers are complex molecules that are resistant to microbial and/or larval degradation (Atelge et al., 2020). Lignin forms a protective barrier around cellulose and hemicellulose hindering their conversion into simple sugars through microbial degradation (Agbor et al., 2011; Atelge et al., 2020). While the BSFL digestive system is inefficient in breaking down lignin, as indicated by the negative correlation between larval weight and lignin content (Liu et al., 2018; Zheng et al., 2012), other studies have reported that BSFL reduced lignin in dairy manure and rice straw by 31 % and 50 %, respectively, (Liu et al., 2021; Rehman et al., 2017a). Nevertheless, by implementing physical (e.g., mechanical and thermal), chemical (e.g., alkaline and acids) and biological (e.g., bacteria and fungi) pretreatments, biowaste could be more digestible for larvae and/or microorganisms in the biowaste or larval digestive tract (Peguero et al., 2022).

Physical pretreatments, such as thermal and mechanical, require energy but offer the advantage of not needing the use of additional compounds, such as chemicals (e.g. HCL, NaOH) or microbial inoculums in order to modify lignocellulosic characteristics (Atelge et al., 2020). Thermal pretreatment (>100 °C, 15–20 mins, 2–9 bar pressure) can improve biowaste digestibility by enhancing the solubilization of organic matter, however these treatment conditions may not be suitable for BSFL because of the inactivation of potentially beneficial microorganisms (Peguero et al., 2022). Since the biowaste microbial community contributes to the bioconversion performance (Gold et al., 2020b), lower temperatures and longer holding times (e.g. 80–90 °C for > 60 min) with a lower impact on the microbial community may be more suitable for BSFL biowaste treatment (Appels et al., 2010; Peguero et al., 2022). These pretreatment conditions (e.g. 80–90 °C for > 60 min) have previously demonstrated positive impacts for other bioprocessing technologies, such as 60 % increase in biogas production from agricultural crops and residues and 14–18 % increase in release of humic substances during composting of dairy manure (Huang et al., 2019; Menardo et al., 2012; Zhu et al., 2021).

Alternatively, mechanical pretreatment, such as milling, could improve larval performance, by reducing the biowaste particle size, increasing the surface area and bulk density of the biowastes, and potentially reducing cellulose crystallinity. These different effects could promote microbial activity and increase degradability by biowaste microorganisms (Atelge et al., 2020; Mshandete et al., 2006). Reducing particle size to ≤ 2 mm for manures, fruit/vegetable waste, and crop and harvesting residues increased methane production by 16–65 % compared to the untreated control (Angelidaki and Ahring, 2000; Menardo et al., 2012; Mshandete et al., 2006; Sharma et al., 1988).

More research is needed on the effectiveness of thermal and mechanical biowaste pretreatment for different BSFL biowastes with different lignocellulosic, nutrient and microbial contents and compositions as well as process conditions (e.g., temperature, holding time, particle size), which all have been shown to influence pretreatment outcomes (Agyeman and Tao, 2014; Menardo et al., 2012). Few studies have examined the effects of thermal (Isibika et al., 2019; Liew et al., 2022) and mechanical (Palma et al., 2019; Yakti et al., 2023) pretreatment on BSFL biowaste treatment. For example, Liew et al. (2022) found thermal pretreatment of waste activated sludge (e.g., >75 °C, >1h) increased BSFL larval weight by 45–292 % compared to the untreated control (Liew et al., 2022). However, one study has found that higher

temperature pretreatment (e.g., 120 °C) of banana peels negatively impacted larval weight by 15 % (Isibika et al., 2019). For mechanical pretreatment, reducing particle size of wheat straw from 3 mm to < 1 mm and almond hulls from 6 mm to 4 mm decreased larval weight by 32 % and 10 %, respectively (Palma et al., 2019; Yakti et al., 2023). However, many studies initially reduce particle size of the selected biowastes and do not compare results to the untreated control, complicating drawing robust conclusions of the effect of particle size reduction on BSFL biowaste processing (Laganaro et al., 2021; Liland et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2021; Palma et al., 2019).

This study assessed the impact of thermal and mechanical pretreatment on BSFL bioconversion with cow manure, spent grain and grass clippings. It was hypothesized that thermal and mechanical pretreatment would increase larvae performance. Furthermore, it was hypothesized that mechanical pretreatment would promote microbial growth and activity in the substrate due to the particle size reduction. Overall, this research sought to contribute to biowaste management by improving the bioconversion efficiency of BSFL on low-value fibrous biowastes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Source of biowastes

BSFL substrates used were spent grain, cow manure, and grass clippings, previously described in detail by Peguero et al. (2023). These substrates were selected due to their high lignocellulosic composition (>45 % DM, sum of hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin) as shown in (Table 1) (Peguero et al., 2023).

2.2. Thermal pretreatment

Substrates were treated at 90 °C for 0.5, 1 and 4 h and compared to an untreated control. A substrate temperature of 90 °C was selected as this temperature was previously shown to increase larval performance (Liew et al., 2022). The substrate (1–2.5 kg wet mass) was distributed in similar amounts across plastic bags. Prior to immersion, the weight and initial temperature of the biowaste in each bag was recorded. The treatment involved immersing the substrates in sealed plastic bags within a water bath filled with deionized water at 90 °C. The bags filled with the substrates were attached to a perforated metal sheet, to ensure that the substrate was completely submerged in the water bath (Fig. 1a). A lid was used to minimize evaporation and maintain water temperature. To ensure thermal consistency, temperature was measured with a thermometer in one of the substrate-filled bags. The timer for the pretreatment duration was initiated once the substrate temperature reached 90 °C (± 1 °C).

Table 1

Physicochemical composition of spent grain, cow manure and grass clippings (Peguero et al., 2023). Data displayed are mean \pm standard deviation (n = 3–4). Results are given in % DM.

Parameters	Spent grain	Cow manure	Grass clippings
Moisture content	74.5 \pm 0.3	91.0 \pm 0.0	74.0 \pm 0.3
Organic matter	95.5 \pm 0.1	81.8 \pm 0.6	89.6 \pm 0.3
Hemicellulose	33.6 \pm 0.6	17.3 \pm 2.3	18.6 \pm 2.1
Cellulose	17.5 \pm 0.2	24.2 \pm 1.1	21.4 \pm 1.9
Lignin	8.2 \pm 0.6	10.7 \pm 0.8	7.3 \pm 0.7
Protein	24.5 \pm 0.2	9.1 \pm 0.1	14.0 \pm 0.4
TOC	49.3 \pm 0.5	42.2 \pm 0.3	43.8 \pm 0.5
TN	3.9 \pm 0.04	2.1 \pm 0.02	3.1 \pm 0.1
C/N ratio	12.6 \pm 0.1	19.9 \pm 0.2	14.4 \pm 0.4

TOC: total organic carbon; TN: total nitrogen; C/N ratio: Carbon/nitrogen ratio.

(a) Thermal pretreatment setup

(b) Mechanically pretreated substrates

Untreated

2-mm

1-mm

0.5-mm

Spent grain

Grass clippings

Fig. 1. (a) Set up of thermal pretreatment using a water bath. (b) Images of the different mechanical treatment conditions for spent grain and grass clippings.

2.3. Mechanical pretreatment

Two mechanical pretreatment experiments were performed with grass clippings and spent grain. In the first experiment, the substrates (3–4 kg) were reduced using a milling screen size of 0.5, 1 and 2 mm and compared to untreated (i.e., without pretreatment). Based on the observed effect of particle size on BSFL bioconversion rate, a follow-up experiment compared untreated substrates to substrates milled using a screen size of 0.5 mm. Substrates were milled (6,000–10,000 rpm, ZM 200, Retsch, Germany) following freezing by dry ice. For spent grain, a 2:1 ratio and for grass clippings, a 3:1 ratio was used (dry ice: substrate). After pretreatment the substrates were stored at -20°C until further use. Images of the substrates before and after mechanical pretreatment can be found in (Fig. 1b).

2.4. Substrate physical properties

Bulk density and particle size distribution were analyzed for the mechanically treated substrates. Particle size distribution were determined on a volume-basis by static light scattering by an external laboratory (Luzern University of Applied Sciences, Luzern, Switzerland) using a Beckman Coulter LS 13 320 Laser Diffraction Particle Size Analyzer with Universal Liquid Module with a maximum detection of $2000\ \mu\text{m}$ and was conducted in duplicate or triplicate. Characteristic particle size distribution values (D10, D50, and D90) were determined from volume-based size distributions (Table 2). The D10, D50 and D90 are the specific percentiles used to describe the particle size distribution. They provide insight into the percentage of particles that are above or below a specific particle diameter (Ward et al., 2023). For all three-screen sizes of the centrifugal mill (0.5, 1 and 2 mm), the particle size analysis revealed much smaller particles than the initial screen size.

Table 2

Particle size distribution of spent grain and grass clippings was analyzed for treatments corresponding the centrifugal mill screen sizes of: 0.5, 1 and 2 mm. The percentiles D10, D50, and D90 are used to describe the particle size distribution on a volume basis. D50 is the median particle diameter, 10 % of the sample is smaller than D10 and 90 % of the sample is smaller than D90. Samples could not be analyzed for particles exceeding 2000 μm . Data displayed are the mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 2\text{--}3$).

Substrate	Treatment (mm)	D10 μm	D50 μm	D90 μm
Spent grain	2.0	83.9 \pm 32.7	463.1 \pm 34.4	1045.0 \pm 21.2
	1.0	74.4 \pm 22.3	396.1 \pm 18.8	858.7 \pm 41.3
	0.5	13.17 \pm 13.4	139.5 \pm 7.7	425.4 \pm 12.0
Grass clippings	2.0	57.2 \pm 27.6	255.1 \pm 86.0	635.4 \pm 82.7
	1.0	50.0 \pm 3.7	249.4 \pm 11.1	595.3 \pm 20.8
	0.5	22.8 \pm 0.4	157.0 \pm 2.7	429.8 \pm 2.2

Since the results for grass clippings between the 1-mm and 2-mm screen sizes were similar, the results from the 1-mm will not be presented in the results section. It is importante to note, due to the detection limit, particles $>2000 \mu\text{m}$ were not detected.

Bulk density was determined in triplicate in spent grain and grass clippings for all treatments (i.e., untreated, and 2-mm, 1-mm and 0.5-mm particle size). Bulk density was determined as the ratio of the substrate in a known volume (140 mL) divided by the wet weight (approx. 20–130 g).

2.5. Source of BSFL

The black soldier fly neonates had the same age (hatching within 24 h) and were sourced from the research colony at Eawag (Dübendorf, Switzerland) maintained according to [Dortmans et al. \(2017\)](#). All neonates were reared under controlled environmental conditions, with a temperature of 28 °C and relative humidity of 70 %. The neonates were fed on chicken feed (60–75 % moisture content, UFA 620, Switzerland) for 5–7 days until reaching a mean individual weight of 1–3 mg DM. The larvae were then separated and transferred to the different feeding substrates and treatments (i.e., untreated and pretreated substrates).

2.6. Larval feeding experiment

Larval feeding experiments were conducted with untreated and pretreated substrates with three to four replicates per treatment. In the first feeding experiments, larvae were reared in plastic containers (diameter: 7.5 cm, height: 11 cm) covered with a mosquito net with 35 mg DM substrate/larvae/day for nine days ([Gold et al., 2020a](#); [Peguero et al., 2023](#)). In the second mechanical pretreatment experiment, larvae were reared at 35 mg DM/larvae/day (spent grain), and 23 mg DM/larvae/day (grass clippings) for six days. In the second mechanical pretreatment feeding experiment, slightly larger containers measuring 21 cm x 15 cm x 12 cm were used and covered with a mosquito net. For all experiments, a larval density of 2.5 larvae/cm² was used ([Gold et al., 2020a](#); [Peguero et al., 2023](#)). The substrates were brought to a temperature of 22–28 °C prior to adding larvae. For each replicate, larvae were weighed, and transferred to the substrate-filled plastic containers. During the first two feeding experiments (thermal and mechanical), the temperature and relative humidity in the climate chamber were 28 °C and 70 %, respectively. In the second mechanical pretreatment experiment, the ambient temperature and humidity in the rearing room were 30 °C and 50–70 %, respectively ([Fig. S-1](#)) and monitored using a temperature data logger (Testo GmbH, Austria), and substrate temperature was monitored using ibuttons (Mouser Electronics, Germany), and

capsules (Mouser Electronics, Germany).

Larvae were manually harvested from the residues, counted, and weighed. After determining the fresh weight, larvae were inactivated at 105 °C for 5 min and then dried in a laboratory oven at 60 °C for two days ([Rehman et al., 2017a](#); [Rehman et al., 2017b](#)). Residues were dried at 60 °C until weight remained constant. Both the dried larvae and the residues were then weighed and stored at 4 °C for further analyses. Based on larval numbers and DM of the substrate, residue and larvae, common rearing performance parameters, including survival rate, final larval weight, bioconversion rate, protein conversion efficiency, and waste reduction were calculated according to ([Gold et al., 2020a](#)). The hemicellulose degradation was calculated using the following equation ([Liu et al., 2021](#)):

Hemicellulose degradation (% DM) =

$$1 - \frac{\text{mass}_{\text{residue}} (\text{g DM}) \times \text{hemicellulose content}_{\text{residue}} (\% \text{ DM})}{\text{mass}_{\text{substrate}} (\text{g DM}) \times \text{hemicellulose content}_{\text{substrate}} (\% \text{ DM})}$$

2.7. Substrate, residue and larval physicochemical analyses

Moisture content and fiber were analyzed in the substrate and residue. Larvae were analyzed for moisture and protein content. All physicochemical analyses were conducted in triplicate or quadruplicate. Moisture content of the substrate was determined as the weight loss of three grams of wet sample by overnight oven drying at 105 °C. Prior to analyzing fiber content, substrates and residues were dried at 60 °C until weight remained constant and milled to 1 mm (10,000 rpm, Retsch ZM 200, Germany). Fiber analyses included neutral detergent fiber (Van Soest et al., 1991), acid detergent fiber (AOAC, 1977) and acid detergent lignin (AOAC, 1977) using 0.5 g dried sample. Neutral and acid detergent fiber were analyzed with a Fibertherm® FT12 system (Gerhardt Analytical Systems, Germany) ([Peguero et al., 2023](#)). Acid detergent lignin was analyzed with the remaining residue following acid detergent fiber which was soaked in 72 % H₂SO₄ for three hours. To determine each lignocellulosic fraction (hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin) formulas provided in [Peguero et al. \(2023\)](#) were used. Nitrogen of the larvae was determined using 0.7 g of dried sample with a C/N analyzer (Trumac CN, LECO Instruments, Germany) and larval protein was calculated using a conversion factor of 4.67 ([Janssen et al., 2017](#)).

2.8. Microbial respiration

The first experiment demonstrated that particle size influenced larval performance which could be due to increased microbial activity due to altered physical substrate characteristics. As a proxy for microbial activity, microbial respiration (i.e., CO₂) was estimated in the second larval feeding experiment with untreated and pretreated substrates. The CO₂ production (ppm), including both larval and microbial respiration, was measured for 5 mins from the headspace above the substrate after closing the rearing container with airtight lid using a pre-calibrated wireless CO₂ sensor (PS-3208, Pasco, California) ([Laganaro et al., 2021](#)). Larval CO₂ production was measured with 10–15 g of randomly sampled mixture of larvae and residue from each substrate and treatment condition ([Fig. S-2](#)). The larvae were washed with deionized water to remove substrate residues and then transferred to a 50 mL falcon tube. The CO₂ sensor was then inserted into the top of the 50 mL tube, forming an airtight seal and recorded CO₂ at a frequency of 1 Hz ([Laganaro et al., 2021](#)). The microbial CO₂ production was estimated as the difference between the overall CO₂ production and larval CO₂ production ([Bekker et al., 2021](#)). The CO₂ production was measured once daily over the six-day feeding experiment for biological triplicates. CO₂ production rates (CO₂ mg/min) were calculated from the slope of the linear regression of CO₂ starting from 2 min, when the sensor stabilized, until 5 min and considering the headspace volume, number of larvae and volume of the sensor ([Bekker et al., 2021](#)). Calculations can be found in the

Supplementary Material.

2.9. Effect of particle size reduction on microbial numbers

To assess the impact of particle size reduction on microbial numbers, aerobic total viable counts (TVC) (30 °C, 72 h) were estimated in triplicate for untreated substrates, and 0.5-mm milled spent grain and grass clippings on day 0, 3 and 6 of the larval feeding experiment by an external laboratory (Eurofins, Switzerland) (ISO, 2013).

2.10. Data analyses

The data analyses were performed using Microsoft Excel (Version 2022, United States) and R statistical language (R Core Team, 2022, version 4.2.0). The mean and standard deviation of the substrate and residue composition, larvae performance parameters, substrate temperature, CO₂ measurements and microbial counts were calculated.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Thermal pretreatment

Larvae developed on all substrates and treatments with survival rates $\geq 93\%$. The only exception was the untreated cow manure, which had a lower survival rate of 83%, compared to treated cow manure which had survival rates ranging from 93 to 96% (Table 3). These findings are within a similar range of 89–99% reported by previous studies, indicating that the rearing conditions and substrates were suitable for larval rearing (Gold et al., 2020a; Peguero et al., 2023; Rehman et al., 2017b).

Contrary to our expectations, thermal pretreatment (90 °C, 0.5, 1, and 4 h) of all three substrates (Table 3), regardless of treatment time, resulted in either a decrease in bioconversion rate and waste reduction or showed no difference compared to the untreated substrates. Specifically, thermally pretreated substrates decreased larval weight by 19–29%, bioconversion rate by 2–29% and waste reduction by 1–57%, compared to the untreated substrates. Our findings are contrary to those of Liew et al. (2022), who reported an increase in larval weight by 292% with thermally pretreated (90 °C, 16 h) waste activated sludge. Several factors could account for the differences between this study and Liew et al. (2022). These differences include various aspects, such as substrate characteristics (e.g., nutrient and lignocellulosic fiber content and composition), BSFL feeding rate (35 mg DM/larvae/day in this study vs. 22 mg DM/larvae/day in Liew et al. (2022)), larval density (2.5 larvae/cm² in this study vs. 0.3 larvae/cm² in Liew et al. (2022)), duration of experiment (9 days in this study vs. 15 days in Liew et al. (2022)) and

genetic variations.

Thermal pretreatments (<100 °C, >30 mins) have also led to increases in performance metrics of other bioconversion processes such as methane/biogas yields by 30–91% (Appels et al., 2010; Climent et al., 2007; Wang et al., 1997). These improvements have been attributed to increasing soluble proteins and soluble carbohydrates in waste activated sludge by 381–2430% and 351–704%, respectively (Appels et al., 2010; Liew et al., 2022). Due to the neutral or negative larval performance results in this study, soluble nutrients were not analyzed. Therefore, it is not possible to conclude if solubilization of nutrients took place. However, it is evident that if this occurred it did not increase larval performance. The decrease in larval performance in this study may also be attributed to a potential reduction or alteration in microbial numbers and composition by thermal treatment which were not further investigated in this study. BSFL processing is a bioconversion process strongly intertwined with microbially mediated processes in both the biowaste and larval digestive tract (De Smet et al., 2018; Gold et al., 2018). Reduction of microbial numbers, for example by thermal treatment may have neutral, or negative effects on BSFL processing. For example, a complete inactivation of the substrate microbial population by non-thermal pretreatment of food waste decreased bioconversion rates by 30% (Gold et al., 2020b). However, thermal pretreatment of food waste (50–60 °C, 10–30 mins) and fecal sludge (80 °C, 5 mins) had no effect on larval performance compared to the untreated substrates even though TVC decreased by 2.5–4 log₁₀ colony forming units/g (cfu/g) and 2–log₁₀ cfu/g, respectively (Peguero et al., 2021; Van Looveren et al., 2023). Therefore, there might be a threshold where a decrease in microbial numbers affects BSFL performance.

3.2. Mechanical pretreatment

3.2.1. Substrate physical properties

Mechanical pretreatment decreased particle size for both spent grain and grass clippings (Table 2). All D-values were found to be much lower than the screen size of the centrifugal mill (0.5, 1 and 2 mm). This could be due to further particle size reduction caused by collisions between substrate particles, between the screen and wall of the mill (Kotamarthy et al., 2020). Additionally, the detection limit of particle size determination was < 2,000 μm . Therefore, particles above the detection limit were unable to be detected. The D50 of 0.5-mm milled spent grain and grass clippings were 140 μm and 157 μm , respectively (Table 2). The D50 for 1-mm milled spent grain and grass clippings were slightly higher than the lower particle size range as they were 400 μm and 250 μm , respectively. However, there was no difference for the D50 between grass clippings screen sizes 2-mm and 1-mm (Table 2).

As expected, this particle size reduction increased bulk density for

Table 3

BSFL rearing performance metrics on substrates treated at 90 °C for three durations (0.5, 1 and 4 h) and the untreated control. Data displayed are the mean \pm standard deviation (n = 3–4).

Substrates	Treatment	Survival rate %	Larval fresh weight	Larval dry weight	Bioconversion rate	Waste reduction
			mg WM	mg DM	% DM	% DM
Cow manure	Untreated	82.9 \pm 2.8	72.0 \pm 3.8	14.1 \pm 0.6	3.3 \pm 0.2	6.4 \pm 4.2
	0.5 h	96.6 \pm 3.7	56.5 \pm 4.9	10.8 \pm 1.1	3.0 \pm 0.3	7.6 \pm 2.6
	1 h	93.4 \pm 6.9	52.6 \pm 2.2	10.1 \pm 0.6	2.6 \pm 0.3	4.2 \pm 2.5
	4 h	93.4 \pm 4.7	60.6 \pm 0.9	11.8 \pm 0.6	3.1 \pm 0.2	6.3 \pm 3.7
Spent grain	Untreated	99.5 \pm 0.5	137.6 \pm 1.5	42.6 \pm 1.0	12.4 \pm 0.3	53.4 \pm 0.7
	0.5 h	98.6 \pm 2.7	119.4 \pm 4.6	37.8 \pm 1.6	10.8 \pm 0.3	50.9 \pm 2.0
	1 h	99.6 \pm 0.9	135.3 \pm 5.8	35.4 \pm 9.0	10.1 \pm 2.8	52.9 \pm 0.6
	4 h	98.2 \pm 1.5	135.8 \pm 7.0	42.9 \pm 1.8	12.2 \pm 0.4	54.4 \pm 0.8
Grass clippings	Untreated	97.3 \pm 2.0	66.3 \pm 3.6	13.4 \pm 0.7	3.8 \pm 0.3	22.2 \pm 5.5
	0.5 h	95.2 \pm 4.4	54.0 \pm 6.2	11.3 \pm 1.4	3.0 \pm 0.4	13.2 \pm 1.7
	1 h	94.3 \pm 6.7	54.7 \pm 2.6	10.4 \pm 2.6	2.7 \pm 0.8	9.6 \pm 3.4
	4 h	96.4 \pm 2.7	61.9 \pm 3.3	12.8 \pm 0.5	3.6 \pm 0.2	12.9 \pm 2.8

WM: wet mass; DM: dry mass.

both spent grain and grass clippings (Table S-1). The mean bulk density increased from 549 ± 78 g/L for untreated spent grain to 895 ± 35 g/L for 0.5-mm spent grain, and from 146 ± 7 g/L for untreated grass clippings to 562 ± 37 g/L for 0.5-mm grass clippings. Bulk density did not appear to differ between sizes 1- and 2-mm for spent grain. Bulk density could positively or negatively affect aeration and oxygen availability for microorganisms and larvae, but limited research has investigated the impact of these parameters on larval performance (Agnew and Leonard, 2003; Palma et al., 2018). A previous study reported that a higher bulk density (1494 g/L) on 1-mm milled wheat straw negatively impacted larval performance (Yakti et al., 2023). However, the observed negative larval performance could be attributed to the use of the same volume of wheat straw (5.5 %) regardless of the particle size, meaning that more substrate was provided to BSFL with the

lower particle size and higher bulk density, potentially restricting the pore space and aeration within the substrate. When considering adding a fibrous material at different particle sizes, less quantity of the smaller particle size should be used to maintain the same mass, accounting for the higher bulk density (Raichura and McCartney, 2006). More likely, the change in pore space and aeration with particle size and bulk density could have impacted larval performance results. Palma et al. (2018) suggested that aeration can impact BSFL, with increased aeration resulting in 5-fold higher larval DM. Aeration was not measured in this study, but a widely used metric for quantifying aeration in composting, an aerobic bioconversion process most similar to BSFL processing, is free air space (Iqbal et al., 2010). Studies suggest that an optimal free air space in composting of different biowastes is 26–33 % (Eftoda and McCartney, 2004; Iqbal et al., 2010; Kulcu and Yaldiz, 2007). Since

Fig. 2. Bioconversion rate, fresh larval weight, dry larval weight and waste reduction on spent grain (a,c,e,g) and grass clippings (b,d,f,h) and treatments (i.e., untreated and treatments: 2-mm, 1-mm, and 0.5-mm). Data displayed are mean (bold) and replicates (grey) (n = 4). DM: dry mass; WM: wet mass.

aeration, bulk density and particle size can influence BSFL processing, future studies should report these basic substrate parameters. Additionally, future research should investigate the range of free air space and bulk density leading to efficient biowastes treatment by BSFL.

3.2.2. BSFL performance on mechanically pretreated substrates

Mechanical pretreatment had a positive impact on larval performance with spent grain and grass clippings. Similar to thermal pretreatment, survival rates were $\geq 94\%$ and appeared to have no effect between treatments, indicating that the rearing conditions and substrates (untreated and pretreated) were suitable for the larvae (Table S-2). Interestingly, reducing the substrate particle size using a 1-mm screen size increased dry larval weight, bioconversion rate and waste reduction for spent grain and grass clippings by 15–19%, 17–18% and 16–20%, respectively, compared to the untreated (Fig. 2). Further

reducing the particle size using a 0.5-mm screen size increased bioconversion rate and fresh larval weights for spent grain and grass clippings by 44–53% and 13–32% respectively, compared to untreated (Fig. 2).

The improved larval performance with smaller particle sizes could be attributed to several factors. Firstly, the smaller particles may facilitate better microbial metabolism, thereby promoting the breakdown of organic matter by the biowaste microorganisms (Vermeulen et al., 2018). Additionally, the larvae might find smaller particles more easily digestible. Lievens et al. (2023) found that, depending on the larval age and weight, BSFL were able to ingest particles ranging from 20 to 110 μm . Furthermore, Bruno et al. (2020) observed that the mouthparts of the larvae had hooks that allowed them to grasp coarse particles in semi-liquid food and further grind them into more digestible particles. Therefore, it is possible that the larvae were able to ingest these smaller

(a) Spent grain: protein conversion (% DM)

(b) Grass clippings: protein conversion (% DM)

(c) Spent grain: hemicellulose degradation (%)

(d) Grass clippings: hemicellulose degradation (%)

Fig. 3. BSFL larval protein conversion on (a) spent grain and (b) grass clippings and degradation of hemicellulose on (c) spent grain and (d) grass clippings and treatments (i.e., untreated, and high, medium and low particle size). Data displayed are mean with error bars displayed as standard deviation (n = 3–4). Results are given in % DM.

particle sizes, considering that the D10 of both substrates and all treatment conditions were below 100 μm (Table 2), which falls within the range mature BSFL can ingest (Lievens et al., 2023).

Despite the different substrate protein concentrations in spent grain (25 % DM) and grass clippings (14 % DM) as shown in Table 1, the larval protein content was found to be comparable for both substrates (untreated and pretreated) ranging between 32 and 35 % DM (Table S-2). Barragan-Fonseca et al. (2018) had similar observations where substrate protein did not influence larval protein. During the lifespan of BSFL, the protein content of the mature larvae tends to decrease as the fat content increases (Liu et al., 2017). Various factors influence larval protein concentrations such as nutrient composition, larval density, stage of development and feeding rate (Beniers and Graham, 2019; Liu et al., 2017). The larval protein concentrations observed in this study (Table S-

2) are similar to previously reported values of 27–39 % DM (initial protein values adjusted with a conversion factor 4.67 instead of 6.25) (Beniers and Graham, 2019; Nyakeri et al., 2017; Tschirner and Simon, 2015). Larval protein conversion increased by 40 % and 24 % for both 0.5-mm milled spent grain and grass clippings, respectively, compared to the untreated substrates (Fig. 3). This indicates that with lower substrate particle size more total protein for animal feed applications could be produced per unit of biowaste.

Contrary to the findings in this study, Yakti et al. (2023), reported that reducing the particle size of wheat straw below 1 mm resulted in lower fresh larval weight (<80 mg wet weight/larva) compared to using wheat straw particles larger than 3 mm (110 mg wet weight/larva). This decrease in larvae performance could be attributed to a reduction of free air space by reducing particles within the substrate, decreasing aeration

(a) Grass clippings: Daily larval wet mass (mg)

(b) Grass clippings: Microbial respiration (mg CO₂/min)

(c) Grass clippings: residue temperature (°C)

Fig. 4. Influence of mechanical pretreatment (untreated vs. 0.5-mm milled grass clippings) on (a) Mean larval wet mass over the six-day feeding experiment; (b) Microbial respiration of grass clippings measured in mg CO₂/min for days 0, 1, 3, 4 and 6; (c) Substrate temperature during the larval feeding experiment. Displayed are mean with error bars displayed as standard deviation (n = 3).

for the larvae and biowaste microorganisms.

The goal of particle size reduction next to direct ingestion by BSFL is to increase the surface area, thereby increasing substrate accessibility to microorganisms and potentially reducing cellulose crystallinity (Mshandete et al., 2006; Palmowski and Müller, 2000). However, in this study it did not seem that particle reduction had a direct influence on the degradation of the lignocellulosic composition during larval rearing. For instance, BSFL bioconversion degraded 25 % DM of hemicellulose in spent grain and 75 % DM of hemicellulose in grass clippings, with no difference observed among the treatments (Fig. 3). The substantially higher reduction of hemicellulose seen on grass clippings compared to spent grain could indicate a different and more digestible hemicellulose composition. Hemicelluloses are complex polymers composed of various hemicellulosic compounds with varying compositions in different biowastes (Saha, 2003). Furthermore, to understand the mechanisms behind mechanical pretreatment, the crystallinity index of cellulose and measurement of surface area should be assessed to evaluate their influence on enhanced substrate degradability.

3.2.3. Influence of mechanical pretreatment on microbial activity and BSFL performance

To understand the potential beneficial effects of particle size reduction on larval performance, a follow up experiment comparing untreated substrates and 0.5-mm milled spent grain and grass clippings was conducted. The follow-up experiment consisted of measuring microbial respiration, as a proxy for microbial activity, next to larval performance metrics and substrate/residue TVC and temperature. The hypothesis was that particle size reduction increases microbial activity because of greater surface area and accessibility by substrate microorganisms (Palmowski and Müller, 2000), leading to higher microbial respiration for milled compared to untreated substrates.

Mechanical pretreatment of grass clippings increased all larval performance metrics compared to the untreated control (Table S-3). However, the same was not observed for spent grain. Throughout the experiment larvae grown on 0.5-mm milled grass clippings had a consistently higher larval wet weight compared to the untreated control (Fig. 4a). The bioconversion rate was 23 % higher for 0.5-mm milled grass clippings compared to the untreated control. However, this was lower than the 44 % increase in bioconversion rate observed in the previous experiment (section 3.2.2).

In contrast to grass clippings, larval performance metrics were not different between 0.5-mm milled spent grain and the untreated control (Table S-3), which is different to the previous experiment, where 0.5-mm milled spent grain increased bioconversion rate by 53 % compared to the untreated control (Fig. 2). Interestingly, larval wet weight was initially higher with untreated spent grain up to rearing day 4, but larvae were slightly heavier with 0.5-mm milled spent grain on harvest day 6 (Fig. 5a). This highlights that changing the rearing container size and associated parameters can outweigh benefits of mechanical pretreatment for spent grain. For example, the larger container size and new dimensions increased the volume-based larval density from 0.06 larvae/cm³ to 0.2 larvae/cm³ and required reducing the rearing duration from 9 d to 6 d, two parameters that can influence larval growth outcomes (Barragan-Fonseca et al., 2018). While mechanical pretreatment has demonstrated improved larval performance metrics under two slightly different rearing conditions for grass clippings, future research should investigate optimal rearing conditions, such as volume-based larval density (Deruytter and Coudron, 2022).

Mechanical pretreatment influenced microbial respiration dynamics for both substrates, but with opposite effects. In line with our

hypothesis, for grass clippings, 0.5-mm milled grass clippings showed initially higher microbial respiration (Fig. 4b) than untreated on day 1 (6.1 mg CO₂/min vs. 3.4 mg CO₂/min) and day 3 (2.8 mg CO₂/min vs. 1.4 mg CO₂/min). From day 4, microbial respiration was higher in the untreated control than 0.5-mm milled grass clippings (Fig. 4b). This initially higher microbial respiration with 0.5-mm milled grass clippings could suggest that changes in the physical substrate properties by mechanical pretreatment indeed increased microbial activity. As the success of larval growth is intertwined with many microbial processes, larvae could have benefited from this increased microbial activity, being one main reason for the observed increase in larval performance metrics. It was expected that microbial numbers and residue temperature would increase with higher microbial respiration, and that residue temperature was associated with microbial respiration due to the production of metabolic heat by the microbial metabolism as frequently observed in composting (Liang et al., 2003). However, residue TVC (Table S-4) and temperature (Fig. 4c) were similar between 0.5-mm milled grass clippings and untreated grass clippings. The observed residue temperature in grass clippings may have primarily come from the larvae, explaining the similar temperature between untreated and pretreated. As studies have shown that higher larval densities (e.g., >4 larvae/cm²) can elevate residue temperature (Li et al., 2023), future research should explore how different larval densities impact microbial activity.

For spent grain, and opposite to our expectation, mechanical pretreatment of 0.5-mm milled spent grain had initially lower microbial respiration (Fig. 5b) compared to the untreated control on day 0 (2.8 mg CO₂/min vs. 1.2 mg CO₂/min) and day 1 (6.2 mg CO₂/min vs. 2.6 mg CO₂/min). On day 4 and particularly day 6, microbial respiration was higher in mechanically pretreated (8.1 mg CO₂/min) than the untreated control (3.4 mg CO₂/min). Spent grain is a high-moisture material that quickly self-ferments (Mussatto et al., 2006). The gradual decrease in microbial respiration for untreated spent grain could suggest that most easily accessible nutrients were likely consumed. In contrast, 0.5-mm milled spent grain may have facilitated better nutrients availability for substrate microorganisms only by day 6 (Fig. 5b). A limitation to this study is the absence of carbon mass balances, making it difficult to conclude on the influence of particle size reduction on nutrient utilization. Particle size reduction could impact the relative abundance of specific microorganisms (Vermeulen et al., 2018), influencing the overall biodegradation process and nutrient availability within the substrate. Residue TVC (Table S-4) were similar between 0.5-mm milled spent grain and untreated spent grain, but the residue temperature was consistently higher throughout the entire feeding experiment in the untreated spent grain (Fig. 5c). The opposite trend observed regarding microbial respiration following mechanical pretreatment for spent grain compared to grass clippings, could be due to changes in physical properties limiting the provision of air for the microbial metabolism. As highlighted by the physical properties results (see section 3.2.1), mechanical pretreatment drastically increased bulk density, making the material denser and thereby limiting the initial free air space or porosity available in 0.5-mm milled spent grain compared to the untreated control. Consequently, mechanical pretreatment could also decrease microbial respiration and substrate temperature as observed here for spent grain (Fig. 5b,c), which could explain the slightly lower larval weight observed up to rearing day 4 with 0.5-mm milled spent grain (Fig. 5a). However, it should be investigated whether such a reduction in microbial respiration results in higher larval performance metrics in a longer feeding duration, since biowaste microorganisms and BSFL can compete for nutrients. Therefore, it may be desired to minimize microbial respiration and maximize take-up by BSFL. To gain further insights

(a) Spent grain: Daily larval wet weight (mg)

(b) Spent grain: Microbial respiration (mg CO₂/min)

(c) Spent grain: residue temperature (°C)

Fig. 5. Influence of mechanical pretreatment (untreated vs. 0.5-mm milled spent grain) on (a) mean larval wet mass over the six-day feeding experiment; (b) Microbial respiration of spent grain measured in mg CO₂/min for days 0, 1, 3, 4 and 6; (c) Substrate temperature during the larval feeding experiment. Data displayed are mean with error bars displayed as standard deviation (n = 3).

into the interactions between biowaste microorganisms and BSFL, future research should continue to explore mass nutrient flows in relation to other physical properties including particle size, bulk density and free air space, which may play substantial roles in nutrient utilization.

4. Conclusions

The applied thermal pretreatment did not improve BSFL performance for the biowastes tested. Mechanical pretreatment for spent grain had varied effects showing increased larval performance in the smaller containers but no effect when using larger containers with shortened feeding duration. In contrast, grass clippings showed a positive increase in larval performance and protein production after mechanical pretreatment in both instances. Future research should investigate the

influence of larval density in relation to volume rather than surface area, as this could have affected the outcomes of mechanical pretreatment experiments. Additionally, further research should investigate physical properties and its relationship to biowaste microorganisms and BSFL, such as larval and microbial activity, microbial composition, metabolic heat and substrate temperature. Specifically, factors such as bulk density and free air space may provide valuable insights into the aeration requirements within biowastes and their impact on nutrient utilization.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Daniela A. Peguero: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Moritz Gold:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Laura Velasquez:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Mutian Niu:** Methodology. **Christian Zurbrügg:** Conceptualization, Supervision. **Alexander Mathys:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data Availability Statement

All original data supporting the findings of this study are publicly available. Raw data and custom R scripts developed for the analyses and visualizations can be found at: <https://github.com/dapeguero/physical-pretreatment>.

Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2024.02.012>.

References

- Agbor, V.B., Cicek, N., Sparling, R., Berlin, A., Levin, D.B., 2011. Biomass pretreatment: fundamentals toward application. *Biotechnol. Adv.* 29, 675–685. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2011.05.005>.
- Agnew, J.M., Leonard, J.J., 2003. The physical properties of compost. *Compost Sci. Util.* 11, 238–264. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1065657X.2003.10702132>.
- Agveman, F.O., Tao, W., 2014. Anaerobic co-digestion of food waste and dairy manure: Effects of food waste particle size and organic loading rate. *J. Environ. Manage.* 133, 268–274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2013.12.016>.
- Angelidaki, I., Ahring, B.K., 2000. Methods for increasing the biogas potential from the recalcitrant organic matter contained in manure. *Water Sci. Technol.* 41, 189–194. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2000.0071>.
- Appels, L., Degreè, J., Van der Bruggen, B., Van Impe, J., Dewil, R., 2010. Influence of low temperature thermal pre-treatment on sludge solubilisation, heavy metal release and anaerobic digestion. *Bioresour. Technol.* 101, 5743–5748. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2010.02.068>.
- Atelge, M.R., Atabani, A.E., Banu, J.R., Krisa, D., Kaya, M., Eskicioglu, C., Kumar, G., Lee, C., Yildiz, Y.S., Unalan, S., Mohanasundaram, R., Duman, F., 2020. A critical review of pretreatment technologies to enhance anaerobic digestion and energy recovery. *Fuel* 270, 117494. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2020.117494>.
- Barragan-Fonseca, K.B., Dicke, M., van Loon, J.J.A., 2018. Influence of larval density and dietary nutrient concentration on performance, body protein, and fat contents of black soldier fly larvae (*Hermetia illucens*). *Entomol. Exp. Appl.* 166, 761–770.
- Bekker, N.S., Heidelbach, S., Vestergaard, S.Z., Nielsen, M.E., Riisgaard-Jensen, M., Zeuner, E.J., Bahrndorff, S., Eriksen, N.T., 2021. Impact of substrate moisture content on growth and metabolic performance of black soldier fly larvae. *Waste Manage.* 127, 73–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2021.04.028>.
- Beniers, J.J.A., Graham, R.I., 2019. Effect of protein and carbohydrate feed concentrations on the growth and composition of black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*) larvae. *J. Insects as Food Feed* 5, 193–199. <https://doi.org/10.3920/JIFF2018.0001>.
- Bruno, D., Bonacci, T., Reguzzoni, M., Casartelli, M., Grimaldi, A., Tettamanti, G., Brandmayr, P., 2020. An in-depth description of head morphology and mouthparts in larvae of the black soldier fly *Hermetia illucens*. *Arthropod Struct. Dev.* 58, 100969. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asd.2020.100969>.
- Climent, M., Ferrer, I., Baeza, M. del M., Artola, A., Vázquez, F., Font, X., 2007. Effects of thermal and mechanical pretreatments of secondary sludge on biogas production under thermophilic conditions. *Chem. Eng. J.* 133, 335–342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2007.02.020>.
- De Smet, J., Wynants, E., Cos, P., Van Campenhout, L., 2018. Microbial community dynamics during rearing of Black Soldier Fly Larvae (*Hermetia illucens*) and impact on exploitation potential. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 84, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.02722-17>.
- Deruytter, D., Coudron, C.L., 2022. The effects of density on the growth, survival and feed conversion of *Tenebrio molitor* larvae. *J. Insects as Food Feed* 8, 141–146. <https://doi.org/10.3920/JIFF2021.0057>.
- Dortmans, B., Diener, S., Verstappen, B.M., Zurbrügg, C., 2017. Black soldier fly biowaste processing: a Step-by-Step Guide. Swiss Federal. Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology (Eawag), Dübendorf, Switzerland.
- Eftoda, G., McCartney, D., 2004. Determining the critical bulking agent requirement for municipal biosolids composting. *Compost Sci. Util.* 12, 208–218. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1065657X.2004.10702185>.
- Fuhrmann, A., Wilde, B., Conz, R.F., Kantengwa, S., Konlambigue, M., Masengesho, B., Kintche, K., Kassa, K., Musazura, W., Späth, L., Gold, M., Mathys, A., Six, J., Hartmann, M., 2022. Residues from black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*) larvae rearing influence the plant-associated soil microbiome in the short term. *Front. Microbiol.* 13, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.994091>.
- Gold, M., Tomberlin, J.K., Diener, S., Zurbrügg, C., Mathys, A., 2018. Decomposition of biowaste macronutrients, microbes, and chemicals in black soldier fly larval treatment: a review. *Waste Manage.* 82, 302–318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2018.10.022>.
- Gold, M., Cassar, C.M., Zurbrügg, C., Kreuzer, M., Boulos, S., Diener, S., Mathys, A., 2020a. Biowaste treatment with black soldier fly larvae: Increasing performance through the formulation of biowastes based on protein and carbohydrates. *Waste Manage.* 102, 319–329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2019.10.036>.
- Gold, M., von Allmen, F., Zurbrügg, C., Zhang, J., Mathys, A., 2020b. Identification of bacteria in two food waste black soldier fly larvae rearing residues. *Front. Microbiol.* 11, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.582867>.
- Huang, Y., L. D., Shah, G.M., Chen, W., Wang, W., Xu, Y., Huang, H., 2019. Hyperthermophilic pretreatment composting significantly accelerates humic substances formation by regulating precursors production and microbial communities. *Waste Manag.* 92, 89–96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2019.05.021>.
- Iqbal, M.K., Shafiq, T., Ahmed, K., 2010. Characterization of bulking agents and its effects on physical properties of compost. *Bioresour. Technol.* 101, 1913–1919. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2009.10.030>.
- Isibika, A., Vinnerås, B., Kibazohi, O., Zurbrügg, C., Lalander, C., 2019. Pre-treatment of banana peel to improve composting by black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens* (L.), Diptera: Stratiomyidae) larvae. *Waste Manage.* 100, 151–160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2019.09.017>.
- ISO, 2013. ISO 4833-1-Microbiology of the food chain — horizontal method for the enumeration of microorganisms.
- Janssen, R.H., Vincken, J.P., Van Den Broek, L.A.M., Fogliano, V., Lakemond, C.M.M., 2017. Nitrogen-to-Protein conversion factors for three edible insects: *Tenebrio molitor*, *Alphitobius diaperinus*, and *Hermetia illucens*. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 65, 2275–2278. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.7b00471>.
- Kaza, S., Yao, L., Bhada-Tata, P., Van Woerden, F., 2018. What a waste 2.0: A global snapshot of solid waste management to 2050. World Bank Publications.
- Kotamarthy, L., Metta, N., Ramachandran, R., 2020. Understanding the effect of granulation and milling. *Processes* 8.
- Kulcu, R., Yaldiz, O., 2007. Composting of goat manure and wheat straw using pine cones as a bulking agent. *Bioresour. Technol.* 98, 2700–2704. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2006.09.025>.
- Laganaro, M., Bahrndorff, S., Eriksen, N.T., 2021. Growth and metabolic performance of black soldier fly larvae grown on low and high-quality substrates. *Waste Manage.* 121, 198–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2020.12.009>.
- Li, C., Addeo, N.F., Rusch, T.W., Tarone, A.M., Tomberlin, J.K., 2023. Black soldier fly (Diptera: Stratiomyidae) larval heat generation and management. *Insect Sci.* 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1744-7917.13198>.
- Liang, C., Das, K.C., McClendon, R.W., 2003. The influence of temperature and moisture contents regimes on the aerobic microbial activity of a biosolids composting blend. *Bioresour. Technol.* 86, 131–137. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0960-8524\(02\)00153-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0960-8524(02)00153-0).
- Lievens, S., Vervoort, E., Bruno, D., Van der Donck, T., Tettamanti, G., Seo, J.W., Poma, G., Covaci, A., De Smet, J., Van Der Borgh, M., 2023. Ingestion and excretion dynamics of microplastics by black soldier fly larvae and correlation with mouth opening size. *Sci. Rep.* 13, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31176-9>.
- Liew, C.S., Mong, G.R., Abdelfattah, E.A., Raksasat, R., Rawindran, H., Kiatkittipong, W., Mohamad, M., Ramli, A., Yunus, N.M., Lam, M.K., Da Oh, W., Lim, J.W., 2022. Correlating black soldier fly larvae growths with soluble nutrients derived from thermally pre-treated waste activated sludge. *Environ. Res.* 210, 112923. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.112923>.
- Liland, N.S., Biancarosa, I., Araujo, P., Biemans, D., Bruckner, C.G., Waagbø, R., Torstensen, B.E., Lock, E.J., 2017. Modulation of nutrient composition of black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*) larvae by feeding seaweed-enriched media. *PLoS One* 12, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0183188>.
- Liu, X., Chen, X., Wang, H., Yang, Q., Ur Rehman, K., Li, W., Cai, M., Li, Q., Mazza, L., Zhang, J., Yu, Z., Zheng, L., 2017. Dynamic changes of nutrient composition throughout the entire life cycle of black soldier fly. *PLoS One* 12, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0182601>.

- Liu, Z., Minor, M., Morel, P.C.H., Najar-Rodriguez, A.J., 2018. Bioconversion of three organic wastes by Black Soldier Fly (Diptera: Stratiomyidae) Larvae. *Environ. Entomol.* 47, 1609–1617. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ee/nvy141>.
- Liu, C., Wang, C., Yao, H., Chapman, S.J., 2021. Pretreatment is an important method for increasing the conversion efficiency of rice straw by black soldier fly larvae based on the function of gut microorganisms. *Sci. Total Environ.* 762 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144118>.
- Menardo, S., Airoidi, G., Balsari, P., 2012. The effect of particle size and thermal pretreatment on the methane yield of four agricultural by-products. *Bioresour. Technol.* 104, 708–714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2011.10.061>.
- Mshandete, A., Björnsson, L., Kivaisi, A.K., Rubindamayugi, M.S.T., Mattiasson, B., 2006. Effect of particle size on biogas yield from sisal fibre waste. *Renew. Energy* 31, 2385–2392. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2005.10.015>.
- Mussatto, S.I., Dragone, G., Roberto, I.C., 2006. Brewers' spent grain: Generation, characteristics and potential applications. *J. Cereal Sci.* 43, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcs.2005.06.001>.
- Nyakeri, E.M., Ogola, H.J.O., Ayieko, M.A., Amimo, F.A., 2017. Valorisation of organic waste material: Growth performance of wild black soldier fly larvae (*Hermetia illucens*) reared on different organic wastes. *J. Insects as Food Feed* 3, 193–202. <https://doi.org/10.3920/JIFF2017.0004>.
- Palma, L., Ceballos, S.J., Johnson, P.C., Niemeier, D., Pitesky, M., VanderGheynst, J.S., 2018. Cultivation of black soldier fly larvae on almond byproducts: impacts of aeration and moisture on larvae growth and composition. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.9252>.
- Palma, L., Fernandez-Bayo, J., Niemeier, D., Pitesky, M., VanderGheynst, J.S., 2019. Managing high fiber food waste for the cultivation of black soldier fly larvae. *NPJ Sci Food* 3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41538-019-0047-7>.
- Palmowski, L.M., Müller, J.A., 2000. Influence of the size reduction of organic waste on their anaerobic digestion. *Water Sci. Technol.* 41, 155–162. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2000.0067>.
- Peguero, D.A., Mutsakatira, E.T., Buckley, C.A., Foutch, G.L., Bischel, H.N., 2021. Evaluating the microbial safety of heat-treated fecal sludge for black soldier fly larvae production in South Africa. *Environ. Eng. Sci.* 38, 331–339. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ees.2020.0272>.
- Peguero, D.A., Gold, M., Vandeweyer, D., Zurbrügg, C., Mathys, A., 2022. A review of pretreatment methods to improve agri-food waste bioconversion by black soldier fly larvae. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 5, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2021.745894>.
- Peguero, D.A., Gold, M., Endara, A., Niu, M., Zurbrügg, C., Mathys, A., 2023. Evaluation of ammonia pretreatment of four fibrous biowastes and its effect on black soldier fly larvae rearing performance. *Waste Manage.* 160, 123–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2023.01.033>.
- Poveda, J., 2021. Insect frass in the development of sustainable agriculture. A Review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 41 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-020-00656-x>.
- Raichura, A., McCartney, D., 2006. Composting of municipal biosolids: Effect of bulking agent particle size on operating performance. *J. Environ. Eng. Sci.* 5, 235–241. <https://doi.org/10.1139/S06-004>.
- Saha, B.C., 2003. Hemicellulose bioconversion. *J. Ind. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 30, 279–291. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10295-003-0049-x>.
- Sharma, S.K., Mishra, I.M., Sharma, M.P., Saini, J.S., 1988. Effect of particle size on biogas generation from biomass residues. *Biomass* 17, 251–263. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0144-4565\(88\)90107-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0144-4565(88)90107-2).
- Tschirner, M., Simon, A., 2015. Influence of different growing substrates and processing on the nutrient composition of black soldier fly larvae destined for animal feed. *J. Insects as Food Feed* 1, 249–259. <https://doi.org/10.3920/JIFF2014.0008>.
- Rehman, K. ur, Rehman, A., Cai, M., Zheng, L., Xiao, X., Somroo, A.A., Wang, H., Li, W., Yu, Z., Zhang, J., 2017a. Conversion of mixtures of dairy manure and soybean curd residue by black soldier fly larvae (*Hermetia illucens* L.). *J. Clean. Prod.* 154, 366–373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.04.019>.
- Rehman, K. ur, Cai, M., Xiao, X., Zheng, L., Wang, H., Somroo, A.A., Zhou, Y., Li, W., Yu, Z., Zhang, J., 2017b. Cellulose decomposition and larval biomass production from the co-digestion of dairy manure and chicken manure by mini-livestock (*Hermetia illucens* L.). *J. Environ. Manage.* 196, 458–465. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.03.047>.
- UN-Habitat, United Nations Human Settlements, 2010. *Solid Waste Management in The World's Cities: Water and Sanitation in the World's Cities 2010*. Earthscan.
- Van Looveren, N., Verbaet, L., Frooninckx, L., Van Miert, S., Van Campenhout, L., Van Der Borgh, M., Vandeweyer, D., 2023. Effect of heat treatment on microbiological safety of supermarket food waste as substrate for black soldier fly larvae (*Hermetia illucens*). *Waste Manag.* 164, 209–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2023.04.018>.
- Vermeulen, K., Verspreet, J., Courtin, C.M., Haesebrouck, F., Baeyen, S., Haegeman, A., Ducatelle, R., Van Immerseel, F., 2018. Reduced particle-size wheat bran is efficiently colonized by a lactic acid-producing community and reduces levels of *Enterobacteriaceae* in the cecal microbiota of broilers. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 84 <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.01343-18>.
- Vongvichith, B., Morioka, S., Sugita, T., Phousavanh, N., Phetsanghanh, N., Chanthasone, P., Pommachan, P., Nakamura, S., 2020. Evaluation of the efficacy of aquaculture feeds for the climbing perch *Anabas testudineus*: replacement of fishmeal by black soldier fly *Hermetia illucens* prepupae. *Fish. Sci.* 86, 145–151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12562-019-01381-5>.
- Wang, Q., Noguchi, C.K., Kuninobu, M., Hara, Y., Kakimoto, K., Ogawa, H.I., Kato, Y., 1997. Influence of hydraulic retention time on anaerobic digestion of pretreated sludge. *Biotechnol. Tech.* 11, 105–108. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1018472607261>.
- Ward, B.J., Nguyen, M.T., Sam, S.B., Korir, N., Niwagaba, C.B., Morgenroth, E., Strande, L., 2023. Particle size as a driver of dewatering performance and its relationship to stabilization in fecal sludge. *J. Environ. Manage.* 326, 116801 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116801>.
- Yakti, W., Müller, M., Klost, M., Mewis, I., Dannehl, D., Ulrichs, C., 2023. Physical properties of substrates as a driver for *Hermetia illucens* (L.) (Diptera: Stratiomyidae) Larvae Growth. *Insects* 14, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects14030266>.
- Zheng, L., Hou, Y., Li, W., Yang, S., Li, Q., Yu, Z., 2012. Biodiesel production from rice straw and restaurant waste employing black soldier fly assisted by microbes. *Energy* 47, 225–229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2012.09.006>.
- Zhu, N., Gao, J., Liang, D., Zhu, Y., Li, B., Jin, H., 2021. Thermal pretreatment enhances the degradation and humification of lignocellulose by stimulating thermophilic bacteria during dairy manure composting. *Bioresour. Technol.* 319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2020.124149>.